

EPONYMS IN BULGARIAN CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract

First clinical eponyms appeared in 19th century and their number is permanently increasing. The present text does not aim to include all of them in order to make a classification, but to select only the most popular ones and on the basis of their construction to group them in accordance with different patterns used in the process of their formation.

Rezumat

Primele eponime „clinice” au apărut încă în sec. al XIX-lea. Astăzi, numărul lor este într-o permanentă creștere.

În articol, autoarea nu-și propune să cerceteze toate eponimele din această sferă pentru a le clasifica într-un fel sau altul. Ea se mulțumește doar cu cele mai întrebuițate și le supune analizei din perspectiva formării.

The fact that human body remains to be an enigma for human knowledge is really curious. Thousands of years have passed from the day when people were not interested only in the world around them, but also in the world inside them. They focused their attention on their inner space. And a lot of questions began to appear – what is the structure of the body, how different organs and systems function and what the purpose of them is and so on, and so forth.

At the beginning it was very difficult to find any answers to these questions, no matter if the responds are true, or not. As Helen King in her “Greek and Roman Medicine” wrote: “The ancient doctor was expected to diagnose by studying the external signs in order to determine what was happening inside. (...) Everything coming out of the body was examined with interest as a way of finding out what was going on in the mysterious regions inside. (...) There were a few instruments which were used to enable the doctor to see into the body. In the absence of X-rays, scans and blood tests, diagnosis usually had to rely on the patient’s answers to questions and on what everyone could recognize through their senses¹.”

But it soon became clear that only ancient doctors’ senses were not enough to understand all the necessary information and to solve the problems. As a result, new instruments were created and new methods began to be used in order to help human knowledge to reveal the mysteries of human body.

And another difficulty appeared here – this time not in the field of medicine, but it is a linguistic one – how these new instruments and methods to be called, whom to be named after. As a basis for these new terms, of course, the names of their discoverers were used. The word, with which terms of that kind are called, is “eponym”.

Eponyms take an important role in the terminological system of every language. In the sphere of medicine they emerged for the first time in 16th and 17th centuries. Clinical eponyms came into view a little bit later, in 19th century, but their number is permanently increasing².

In the present research it is paid attention on those Bulgarian clinical terms which are the most popular and are familiar even to the ordinary people. That is why the list with clinical eponyms does not claim to be full and complete because the main purpose is an attempt for classification of them to be made.

“Encyclopedic Dictionary from A to Z” by Sergey Vlahov is used for a basic source of information. The selected eponyms and facts about them are compared with the data introduced in “Dictionary of Foreign Words in Bulgarian Language” by A. Millev, B. Nikolov and J. Bratkov, and that shown in “Terminologia Medica Polyglota” (“Medical Terminology in Six Languages”) by Dr. George Arnaudov and “Nova Terminologia Medica Polyglota et Eponymica” (“New Medical and Eponymic Terminology in Seven Languages”) by Petya George Arnaudov.

¹King, 2001, p. 12.

²Tosheva *et alii*, 2000, p. 323.

The list contains eleven eponyms from seven French³ and eleven from four German names, six terms from five British names, five from three Italian personal names, two eponyms from Galenus' name⁴. There is also an eponym with a Russian origin, one with a Dutch origin, one with a Czech origin, and another one with an American origin. All the thirty-nine clinical terms come from the surnames of their discoverers.

In order to be classified⁵, these eponyms are divided into two major groups in accordance to the principles, used in their formation. The first group covers terms formed by the means of conversion or created by combination of root (usually the personal name of the discoverer) and a suffix, carrying its own meaning. Such terms are called monobasic. The second group includes eponyms that are compound terms.

I. Monobasic terms:

1) **created by conversion:** *манту* (разг.) < *Mantoux* (French proper name), *рентген* (разг.) < *Röntgen* (German proper name). All these units are used only in the colloquial speech.

2) created by combination of root and suffix:

A) root + suffix *-ин*: *никотин*⁶. The meaning of the suffix *-ин* is "pertaining to or of".

B) root + suffix *-ела*: *бруцела*, *пастъорела*, *салмонела*⁷.

C) root + suffix *-ия*: *риккетсия*, *листерия*. The suffix *-ия* is with Greek origin (< *-εια*, *-ια*) and is used in forming names of countries, diseases, flowers. It denotes character or condition too⁸.

D) root + suffix *-изация*: *дарсонвализация*, *фарадизация* etc.⁹

E) root + suffix *-графия*: *хайморозграфия*, *рентгенография*¹⁰.

F) root + suffix *-терапия*: *рентгенотерапия*¹¹.

G) root + suffix *-грама*: *рентгенограма*¹² (= *рентгенова снимка*).

H) root + suffix *-скопия*: *рентгеноскопия*¹³.

II. Compound terms

³Joseph Babinski is a French neurologist but with Polish origin.

⁴He is with Greek origin but lived in Ancient Rome as a Roman citizen.

⁵In the process of classification, the eponyms of Bulgarian, used as examples in this article, are presented with their Latin and English equivalents.

⁶In Latin we can find the suffix *-inum*: *nicotinum*. In English – the suffix *-ine*: *nicotine*. The suffix *-inum* usually indicates a relationship of position, possession, or origin. It is added to a noun base (especially a proper name) to form an adjective (to see http://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Category:Latin_suffixes).

⁷In Latin and English we can find the units *Brucella*, *Pasteurella*, *Salmonella*. The suffix *-ella* is added to a noun to form a diminutive of that noun (to see http://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Category:Latin_suffixes).

⁸In Latin and English we can find the suffix *-ia*: *rickettsia*, *listeria* etc. (to see http://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Category:Latin_suffixes).

⁹In Latin and English the Bulgarian suffix *-изация* has the equivalents *-isation/-ization* (Engl.) and *-isatio* (Lat.) (with alternative forms *-atio*, *-tio* and *-io*): *faradisatio*, *darsonvalisatio*, *faradisation*, *darsonvalization*. They are used to form a noun relating to some action (to see http://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Category:Latin_suffixes).

¹⁰In Latin we can find the suffix *-graphia*: *highmorographia*, *roentgenographia* etc. In English – the suffix *-graphy*: *highmorography*, *roentgenography* etc. The suffix *graphia* is with Greek origin and means "something recorded or pictured" (to see http://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Category:Latin_suffixes).

¹¹In Latin we can find the suffix *-therapia* (in *roentgenotherapia* for example), in English – the suffix *-therapy* (in *roentgenotherapy*). The suffix *-therapia* is with Greek origin and means "a course of treatment, therapy" [Arnaudov, 1964, p. 537].

¹²In Latin we can find the suffix *-gramma* (in *roentgenogramma* for example), in English – the suffix *-gram* (in *roentgenogram* and other units). The suffix *gramma* is with Greek origin and indicates something written, drawn, or otherwise recorded, as in electrocardiogram [Rothenberg *et alii*, 2000, p. 243].

¹³In Latin we can find the suffix *-scopia* (in *roentgenoscopia* for example), in English – the suffix *-scopy* (in *roentgenoscopy*). The suffix *-scopia* is with Greek origin and used in compound words, it means "to look, to examine with the help of an instrument" [Arnaudov, 1964, p. 475].

In the Bulgarian clinical compound terms two subgroups could also be distinguished according to their structure. The first one includes compound terms containing an adjective, derivated from a personal name by adding the suffix *-ов(-), -ова, -ово* or *-ев, -ева, -ево*, and a common noun. For example: *Кохов бацил*¹⁴ (сИН. *бацил на Кох, туберкулозна бактерия, туберкулозен бацил*), *граафов фоликул*¹⁵, *галенови препарати*¹⁶ (сИН. *галенични лекарства, неогаленови/новогаленови препарати*¹⁷, *рентгенова снимка*¹⁸ (сИН. *рентгенограма*), *базедова триада*¹⁹ (сИН. *мерзбургска триада*), *хайморова кухина*²⁰ (сИН. *максиларен синус*), *шванова обвивка*²¹ (сИН. *обвивка на Шван, неврилема*), *малпигиев слой*²² (сИН. *производен/герминативен слой; малпигиева мрежа*), *малпигиева мрежа*²³ (сИН. *малпигиев слой*), *евстахиева тръба*²⁴, *фалопиева тръба*²⁵ (сИН. *маточна тръба*), *малпигиево телце*²⁶.

The second subgroup includes compound terms containing a common noun, the preposition *на* (that expresses possession) and a personal name: *бацил на Кох*²⁷ (сИН. *туберкулозна бактерия, туберкулозен бацил, Кохов бацил*), *vlakna на Пуркине*²⁸, *обвивка на Шван*²⁹ (сИН. *шванова обвивка, неврилема*), *проба на Манту*³⁰ (сИН. *реакция на Манту*), *реакция на Манту*³¹ (сИН. *проба на Манту*), *рефлекс на Бабински*³² (сИН. *феномен на Бабински*), *рефлеси на Бехтерева*³³, *тетрада на Фало*³⁴, *триада на Фало*³⁵, *феномен на Бабински*³⁶ (сИН. *рефлекс на Бабински*), *фрактура на Дюпюитрен*³⁷.

¹⁴In Latin - *Kochi Bacillus (Mycobacterium tuberculosis)*, in English - *tubercle bacillus*.

¹⁵In Latin - *graafi folliculus oophorus vasiculosus*, in English - *graafian follicle*.

¹⁶In Latin - *praeparata galenica (galenica (remedia))*, in English - *galenical preparations (galenicals)*.

¹⁷In Latin - *neogalenica (praeparata neogalenica)*, in English - *neogalenicals*.

¹⁸In Latin - *roentgenogramma*, in English - *roentgenogram*.

¹⁹In Latin - *Basedowi trias (Merseburgi trias)*, in English - *Basedow's triad (Merseburg's triad)*.

²⁰In Latin - *Higmori antrum (sinus maxillaris)*, in English - *antrum of Highmore (maxillary sinus)*.

²¹In Latin - *neurilemma*, in English - *neurilemma, sheath of Schwann*.

²²In Latin - *stratum Malpighii (stratum germinativum)*, in English - *Malpighian layer (Malpighian rete)*.

²³In Latin - *stratum Malpighii*, in English - *Malpighian rete (Malpighian layer)*.

²⁴In Latin - *tuba Eustachii (tuba auditiva)*, in English - *Eustachian tube (auditory tube)*.

²⁵In Latin - *tuba Fallopii (tuba uterina)*, in English - *Fallopian tube (oviduct, salpinx)*.

²⁶In Latin - *corpusculum Malpighi (corpusculum renis)*, in English - *Malpighian corpuscle (renal corpuscle)*.

²⁷In Latin - *Kochi Bacillus (Mycobacterium tuberculosis)*, in English - *tubercle bacillus*.

²⁸In Latin - *Purkinje' fibrae*, in English - *Purkinje's fibres*.

²⁹In Latin - *neurilemma*, in English - *neurilemma, sheath of Schwann*.

³⁰In Latin - *Mantoux' testum (Mantoux' reactio)*, in English - *Mantoux test (Mantoux reaction)*.

³¹In Latin - *Mantoux' reactio (Mantoux' testum)*, in English - *Mantoux reaction (Mantoux test)*.

³²In Latin - *Babinski reflexus*, in English - *Babinski's reflex (Babinski's phenomenon)*.

³³In Latin - *Bechterevi/Behterevi reflexus*, in English - *Bechterev's/Behterev's reflexes*.

³⁴In Latin - *Falloti tetralogia*, in English - *Fallot's tetrad*.

³⁵In Latin - *Falloti triad*, in English - *Fallot's trias*.

³⁶In Latin - *Babinski reflexus*, in English - *Babinski's phenomenon (Babinski's reflex)*.

³⁷In Latin - *Dupuytreni fractura*, in English - *Dupuytren's fracture*.

In conclusion we can say that in Latin clinical terminology is followed that the personal name is given a grammatical form for Genitive, singular and that form is added to the common noun. Terms like *Mantoux' testum* and *Mantoux' reactio* are rare here but are the preferred one in "Nova Terminologia Medica Polyglota et Eponymica". Principles for phrase syntax are wavered (*Basedowi trias*, but *stratum Malpighii*). The same is the situation about the usage of capital and small letters. Sometime the adjective is derivated from the name of the discoverer and it is added to the common noun (*praeparata galenica*). In English clinical terminology the adjective is derivated from the scientist's personal name and it is added to the common noun. Often the adjective in English is substantivated.

Two ways for expressing possessiveness are also observed - by "s" and by construction *personal name + preposition "of" + common noun*. In both Latin and English systems the usage of terms formed by the combination of Greek and Latin terminoelements are found.

There are pairs of synonyms just like the Latin and English eponyms *Listeria* and *Listerella* (monobasic terms), and the Bulgarian *шванова обвивка* and *обвивка на Шван* (compound terms). Such types of synonyms are called absolute synonyms or lexical doublets and their meaning and stylistic usage is

Conclusions:

Different patterns of term-formation have different degree of productiveness. The most profitable of all, from the presented types of construction, are those models which are typical for the two subgroups of compound clinical terms. The monobasic Bulgarian eponyms with Greek origin are more creative than those with Latin origin.

It is very interesting how words and language in general, illustrate and depict changes in human knowledge and life. Ancient doctors rely on their senses to feel and understand their patients' pain, while modern medicine relies on innumerable complicated instruments to discover and describe the same – human pain. But neither the ancient doctors, nor contemporary scientists can discover and explain everything³⁸. New facts and innovations are permanently appearing, and the new words (especially new terms), created for naming them, have to be described and classified.

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completely alike [Georgiev et alii, 1996, p. 165]. They could be observed only in scientific terminology [idem, p. 165-166].

³⁸King, 2000, p. 62.